

IMPROVING THE METHODOLOGICAL PREPARATION OF FUTURE PRIMARY TEACHERS TO TEACH STUDENTS BASED ON THE PIRLS INTERNATIONAL ASSESSMENT PROGRAM AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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Abstract. *This article discusses the relevance of improving the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers in our country's education system to teach students based on the PIRLS international assessment program, and the importance of the PIRLS international assessment program, which tests the reading literacy of primary school students in this process.*

Keywords: *PIRLS, education, school, environment, future teacher, student, conscious reading literacy, questionnaire.*

Introduction. The main driving force behind the industrial revolution taking place in the world today is creative thinking. No matter which aspect of society you look at, you will see unparalleled and amazing examples of human creativity. Electric cars, virtual realities, soilless farming - all of these are products of human thinking and imagination. The television, telephone, airplane, even the lamp that we take for granted today were once in the dreams and imaginations of people. Innovations have brought ease and convenience to people's lives. In this way, creativity has become a crucial part of progress. In such a rapidly developing era, the formation of creative thinking skills of students and the formation of elements of a broad worldview are directly related to their conscious reading and comprehension skills. If a child does not consciously understand the main goal of the text being studied, creative research in this area is ineffective. Therefore, extensive work is being carried out to develop conscious reading skills of primary school students. As a clear example of this, we can show that the reading and comprehension skills of students are being tested through the PIRLS international assessment program of our Republic.

The changes being implemented in our country's education sector are aimed at developing students' critical reading and creative thinking skills, improving the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers to teach students based on the PIRLS international assessment program, and ensuring the worthy participation of primary school students in international assessment programs.

Literature review and methodology. Petra Kristi Mulyani, in her own research, considered the role of the curricula used in the country's education system in preparing students for the PIRLS international assessment program, noting that the performance of students in the country participating in the PIRLS international assessment program is closely related to the curricula used in general education schools and, of course, the methodological training of primary school teachers working on the basis of these curricula.

Ying-Chiao Tsai, in her research on the relationship between effective school education and the PIRLS international assessment program, analyzed the relationship between school education and the personal qualities of students and the characteristics of the family in which they grow up, and proved that the effective organization of the educational process at school is a key factor in achieving high student achievement, but that these achievements vary significantly between classes. It is clear from this that the formation of students by primary school teachers

based on modern approaches and preparation for the requirements of international assessment programs not only contributes to the effective organization of the educational process at school, but also to the personal development of students and the development of their higher abilities.

Based on the topic, if we follow the definition given by the author H.K. Ismailova to the concept of "readiness", the concept of "readiness" is defined as "related to the mental functions necessary during the implementation of a certain activity", while L.V. Shkerina evaluates it as previously acquired instructions, knowledge, skills and qualifications and defines it as "preparation for a particular type of activity includes previously acquired instructions, knowledge, skills and qualifications necessary for the application of this activity."

Researchers Ye.A.Levanova, S.M.Fayrushina highlighted important characteristics of the technology for the formation of a teacher's practical readiness for interaction: the presence of a clearly and diagnostically defined goal, a correctly measured result of activity, a system of practical tasks related to the knowledge of the content of the activity, a guiding system and methods for solving them, the presence of a sufficiently strict consistency, logic and stages of activity, individual group stratification of students' educational and professional activities, showing the methods of interaction of participants at each stage, motivational support for their activities based on the realization of personal qualities of students and teachers (free choice, creativity, competitiveness, life and professional meaning); indicating the boundaries of students' algorithmic and creative activities, possible restrictions from various rules.

Z.K. Ismailova divides the components of the student's readiness for pedagogical activity into the following areas:

1. Psychological preparation (motivational, volitional, emotional and other psychological processes and the state of the individual's attitude to future activity);
2. Theoretical preparation (the presence in the subject's mind of a clear idea of the activity, its essence, its tasks, principles, content, forms and methods).
3. Practical preparation (a set of skills necessary for the effective implementation of one or another pedagogical activity).

Pedagogical preparation is a set of personal qualities and is a preparation for the independent organization of professional and pedagogical activity at a high level. From this we can conclude that pedagogical preparation is the effective organization of all types of pedagogical activity, their orientation towards the goals of personal development and comprehensive development.

Taking into account that the PIRLS international assessment program is focused on conscious reading literacy, the development of conscious reading, information analysis, and inference skills of future teachers is an important factor in improving the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers for teaching students based on the PIRLS international assessment program.

Results obtained and their analysis. Thus, in the process of working on the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers, the work of primary school students on international assessment programs is manifested as a component of the implementation of several areas. In particular, the task of instilling in primary education subjects through practical teaching, systematic and consistent teaching, teaching based on examples and special exercises, reading and understanding literary and informational texts, preventing various errors and correcting them through the performance of practical tasks on oneself plays an important role. Taking into account the age and psychological characteristics of students, it is considered a modern requirement to develop advanced teaching methods and a system of exercises that help them to thoroughly master all the topics of the curriculum, to think independently, express their opinions freely, listen to the

opinions of others, reflect, distinguish the most important ones from them, put forward their own opinion, justify it, generalize and conclude, arouse interest in the use of language material by the teacher, create a need for its practical use, and are recognized as a factor in increasing educational efficiency.

The PIRLS international assessment program is a large international assessment program that allows for international comparison of data on the level of development of reading comprehension skills of 4th grade students of participating countries by testing them, and provides analysis that serves state policy in improving the education and training system.

The PIRLS study is considered the most effective monitoring of primary school graduates, and the PIRLS tasks are recognized by the international community as the best modern, reading literacy assessment program for students who love to read. Therefore, teaching primary school students based on international assessment programs makes a worthy contribution to the effectiveness of education and the prosperity of the country. Since the implementation of this task is the main task of primary school teachers, it is important today to improve the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers for teaching based on international assessment programs.

Reading literacy: A person's ability to understand and respond to information presented in text form, the ability to use the information they have read for their own purposes, and to increase their knowledge and capabilities in the process of active participation in society. The concept of reading literacy has a broad meaning. The goal of this direction is to determine the student's skills in understanding texts on a variety of topics, such as excerpts from a given work of art, biographies, letters, documents, articles from newspapers and magazines, various manuals, geographical maps, and diagrams, pictures, maps, graphs, and tables designed to explain the text, thinking about its content, evaluating the content of the text, and expressing their own opinions about what they have read.

Why is improving the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers to teach based on the requirements of the PIRLS international assessment program so important in today's education system? Because the ability of primary school students to understand the information they receive from the texts they read and to apply this information in life significantly affects the fate of each child and the prospects of the country. The results of research show that a high level of reading and text comprehension literacy of a primary school graduate affects his or her subsequent, deeper knowledge at the next stages of education, especially in higher education.

In 2021, our country's primary school students participated in the PIRLS international assessment program for the first time, and the analysis of the recorded results and the conclusions drawn served as the basis for setting the necessary goals for the development of the education sector, identifying factors affecting the implementation of these goals, and developing important recommendations for raising the conscious reading literacy of students to a high level. Primary school teachers play the main decisive role in implementing these tasks. Therefore, improving the methodological preparation of future primary school teachers to teach students based on the PIRLS international assessment program is of great importance in today's education system.

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